

ISSN: 2349-8269

DIMAPUR GOVERNMENT COLLEGE

Journal

Volume IX | Issue No.1 | 2023

Peer-Reviewed Journal

ISSN: 2349-8269

DIMAPUR GOVERNMENT COLLEGE JOURNAL
2023

Volume IX, Issue No.1

Heritage Publishing House

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A Study on the GST Awareness among Business Retailers in Nagaland with Specific Reference to Dimapur District

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Abstract

Recently India witnessed a change in its indirect tax regime. There was much anarchy in the country as people did not have much knowledge and understanding for this new system, i.e., GOODS AND SERVICE TAX (GST). The Small and medium business persons (SBP) were the most affected segment in terms of the changes to be done because of GST. In this paper an attempt has been made to observe the awareness and perceptions about GST among Small retailers. Also, how far government is successful to get acquainted small retailers about GST particularly focused on small retailers' perception about the new the tax system (e.g., Transparency, burden on SBP's), and its administration. The results shows that initially there was low level awareness but as time progressed, the level of awareness also increased among the small retailers about GST, not all small retailers perceived the GST system as being reasonably simple or easy to understand. However, it was observed that most of the small retailers were making efforts to get acquainted with the new tax regime since starting, i.e., when the GST bill was passed. Many Small retailers also specified that they depend on accounting software for keeping a proper record of their GST transactions. Though

GST was considered simple, there are some compliance costs which give burden to Micro and small business owners. This study is qualitative in nature and it is observation-based research.

Keywords: Perception, GST, Awareness, Small Businesses, IGST, SGST.

Introduction

India earlier had a dual system of taxation of goods and services which was fairly dissimilar from the present twin GST system. In India, the concept of GST was envisioned in 2004 by Kelkar Committee. The Kelkar Committee introduced the twin GST system, the committee was influenced that they will be able to tax nearly all the goods and services which will enhance revenue for the government. It is a major improvement in the tax structure in India where there are lots of issues related to transparency. In any country, the main basis of revenue is the tax and for good economic development, it is essential to have a good taxation system. In 1980, India started its tax system. Since its independence, India has faced many issues because of the complexities of the indirect tax system; GST was a great move in the Indian economy as some of the complexities as perceived are resolved in the present GST structure. As GST has replaced all indirect taxes to come up with simplified unique tax. SBPs pay a lot of indirect taxes such as VAT, Service tax, sales tax, octroi and luxury tax. The Goods and Services Tax (GST) will be acting as a much-needed stimulant for economic growth in India by removing all indirect taxation. It will also eradicate the cascading result of taxes. The implementation of GST will increase the ease of conducting business within India and also across borders. The implementation of GST is dual i.e., central GST which is levied by the Centre and state GST is levied by the state. When GST is implemented, all other indirect taxes are discontinued and now there is only one tax which is GST which is under the strict control of the central government. This system helps in eliminating tax-based thefts and makes the taxation system much clearer. Narayanan, (1991) stated